

Sustainable and recyclable thermoplastic sizing based on aqueous dispersion

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ABSTRACT

In the aerospace industry, thermosetting composites, such as polyepoxide/carbon fibers, will be in future fully replaced with recyclable thermoplastic composites like polyetheretherketone/carbon fibers. However this technological transition will require processing to be adapted to this new and recyclable material. These include the sizing, consisting on a coating of the carbon fiber by a suited polymer which will allow continuity between the fiber and the matrix. The current research focuses on the thermoplastic sizings mainly formulated in organic solvents.

However, in the context of a more eco-friendly approach (REACH), the formulation of sizing based on aqueous dispersions represents the best alternative. This work will illustrate how we succeeded to optimize an eco-friendly aqueous dispersion for thermoplastic sizing at industrial scale. We will present the adjustment of the sizing formulations, and the influence of the surfactants and their concentration on the size of the particles and the stability of the aqueous dispersions of PEI. The resulting formulations will be discussed in terms of particle size measured by dynamic light scattering. Finally the sizing was evaluated by electron microscopy observations of the carbon fibers with thermoplastic sizing.

1 INTRODUCTION

In aeronautic field, composite materials are more and more used. We remember the first flight of A350, a plane composed at 53% of composites. That's why more and more researches are developed to improve mechanical properties of these materials[1-3]. One of the solutions is the sizing of carbon fibres to improve adhesion between fibers and polymeric matrix[4-6]. Sizing is a very thin film of polymer (between 0.1 and 1 μm)[7] that coats carbon fibers.

In a context of a more eco-friendly approach, the coating polymer is dispersed in water. This aqueous dispersion is made from an emulsion/solvent evaporation process where the polymer is solubilised in volatile organic solvent that is immiscible with water[8, 9]. When solvent evaporate, polymer particles are formed, and dispersed by amphiphilic molecules in water.

The stability of these particles is affected by numerous experimental parameters and conditions. A rapid optimization with quantitative structure-property relationship (QSPR) method has already been developed in our laboratory to optimize the stability of the dispersion[10]. Indeed, we succeeded in using artificial neural networks to limit influent parameters on the stability of dispersion and save time to test this dispersion for the sizing of carbon fibres.

In this study, the preparation and characterization of the dispersion is discussed and a brief description of the optimization method is given to select the sizing dispersion which will be analyzed by microscopy (TEM, SEM and AFM) and IR spectrometry on carbon slab or carbon fibres.

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

3.1 Materials

PEI Ultem 1000 is purchased from Goodfellow. Sorbitan monostearate is obtained from Alfa Aesar. Benzalkonium chloride, chloroform and dichloromethane were purchased from Sigma Aldrich. All components are used without any further purification process.

3.1 Methods

Dynamic Light Scattering (DLS). Photon correlation spectroscopy (PCS) is used to determine the mean diameter of the particles and their polydispersity index. A Zetasizer® Nano ZS, Malvern PCS Instruments is used at z scattering angle of 173° . Samples were diluted with 100 μL of dispersion and 1 mL of ultrapure water.

LUMiFuge®. The Stability Analyser LUMiFuge® is an instrument of choice for process optimization which uses centrifugal force to demix dilute or concentrated suspensions/emulsions. With SEPView® v6.0 software, the speed of clarification can be calculated and the stability of suspensions/emulsions can be determined.

Transmission Electron Microscopy (TEM). The TEM images were obtained under vacuum on a Hitachi HT 7700 electron microscope at CMEAB (Center for Electron Microscopy Applied to Biology) in Toulouse (France). Samples were contrasted with an aqueous solution of 2%wt of uranyl acetate.

Quantitative Structure-Properties Relationship (QSPR). All experimental data were taken from 28 different experiments that were at least duplicated. The considering experimental input parameters were time of emulsification (t_{em}), shear speed of emulsification step (S_{em}), temperature of emulsification step (T_{em}°), temperature of evaporation step (T_{evap}°), type of stirrer during evaporation step (T_{sti}), surfactant concentration (C_s), co-surfactant concentration (C_{co-s}) and anti-foam agent concentration (C_{af}) (Table 1). The studied property parameter (output) was the speed of clarification given by the LUMiFuge®. The data are coded and normalized (Table 1). The artificial neural networks software used for this study was SNNS (Stuttgart Neural Network Simulator) v4.2, developed at the University of Stuttgart, Germany.

Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM). The SEM images were also obtained at CMEAB in Toulouse on an ESEM Quanta 250 FEG electron microscope. Samples were metallized before observation.

Atomic Force Microscopy (AFM). The dispersions were dropped off carbon slabs or carbon fibres, and dried in an oven at 100°C for 5 minutes. Fibers were fixed on a glass slide with double adhesive tape. They have been analysed in intermittent contact mode (probe RTESPA from Bruker, k range 20-80 N/m) at air on a NanoWizard®III from JPK coupled with an optical microscope ZEISS AxioObserver A1.

Infra-Red Spectroscopy. The iN10MX ThermoScientific spectrometer is used in reflection, coupled with optical microscopy, for IR cartography on carbon slab.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Preparation of the aqueous dispersions

The emulsion/solvent evaporation process was used to prepare the aqueous dispersions of PEI. This process is widely used in the pharmaceutical industry[11-13] but it is relatively recent in the aeronautic

field[9, 14]. The two-step process is described in figure 1. First, the polymer solution is added to aqueous solution and emulsified with an Ultra-Turrax® device during 30 or 60 minutes. In the same time, the volatile organic solvent evaporates and the polymer precipitated. To insure the total disappearance of organic solvent in solution, the system is maintained under magnetic or mechanical stirring during 12 hours. At the end, we can obtain an aqueous dispersion of thermoplastic polymer particles.

Figure 1: Scheme of emulsion/solvent evaporation process.

The particle stability is affected by numerous experimental parameters and conditions (Fig. 2) and it is needful to use a predictive model to limit the number of experiments. We choose to use Quantitative Structure-Property Relationship (QSPR) with artificial neural network (ANN) to optimize the stability of the dispersions.

Figure 2: General parameters and conditions affecting particle stability.

3.2 Optimization of the dispersion by QSPR method

ANN are widely used in biological field with the QSAR (Quantitative Structure-Activity Relationship) method. The first applications of QSAR methodology dates back to 1964 with the work of Hansch[15] and the models proposed by Free and Wilson[16]. Hansch and Fujita developed models directly linking properties of various compounds (hydrophobic, sterical...) with biological activity on different cells. As for Free and Wilson, they proposed a mathematical model based on four equations and three unknowns linking with substituent contribution on toxicity of analgesic compounds. One of the first

works with ANN were those of Hiller et al.[17] in 1971. They used the concept of perceptrons to link physiological activity with effect of different substituents for dioxane derivatives. Architecture of ANN and their representative approach to describe chemical structure are varied but multilayer feed-forward neural networks with back propagation have proved their efficiency in QSAR and QSPR studies. This type of neural networks is used in this study with SNNS (Stuttgart Neural Network Simulator) v4.2 software to model the relationships between input parameters (see table 1) and the output parameter: the speed of clarification given by the LUMiFuge® device. This speed of clarification determines the stability of the dispersion.

Table 1: Details of input parameters

Parameter name	Abbreviation	Range level : coded level
Time of emulsification (min)	t_{em}	30 : 0 ; 60 : 1
Stirring rate of emulsification step (rpm)	S_{em}	3000 : 0.25 ; 5000 : 0.417 ; 7800 : 0.65 ; 9000 : 0.75 ; 12000 : 1
Temperature of emulsification step (°C)	T_{em}°	25 : 0.625 ; 40 : 1
Temperature of evaporation step (°C)	T_{evap}°	25 : 0.625 ; 40 : 1
Type of stirrer during evaporation step	T_{sti}	magnet : 0 ; motor : 1
Surfactant concentration (mol/L)	C_s	0.57 : 0.57 ; 1 : 1
Co-surfactant concentration (mol/L)	C_{co-s}	0 : 0 ; 0.04 : 0.160 ; 0.06 : 0.24 ; 0.12 : 0.48 ; 0.24 : 0.96 ; 0.25 : 1
Anti-foam agent concentration (mol/L)	C_{af}	0 : 0 ; 0 : 0.12

The first step in the QSPR method is to define the most important parameters influencing the speed of clarification. For this, we built a neural network, named NN0 (see table 2 and 3), composed by 8 input nodes in the input layer and 1 node in the output layer without any hidden layers. This learning pattern was made with 28 different experiments.

Table 2: Data used by the different neural networks

Data set	Number of input parameters	Type of input parameters
1	8	$t_{em}, S_{em}, T_{em}^{\circ}, T_{evap}^{\circ}, T_{sti}, C_s,$ C_{co-s}, C_{af}
2	5	$S_{em}, T_{em}^{\circ}, T_{evap}^{\circ}, C_s, C_{af}$
3	4	$S_{em}, T_{em}^{\circ}, C_s, C_{af}$
4	4	$S_{em}, T_{em}^{\circ}, T_{evap}^{\circ}, C_s$
5	3	$S_{em}, T_{em}^{\circ}, C_s$
6	2	S_{em}, C_s

Table 3: Architecture of neural networks and data set used

Neural Networks	Data set	Number of nodes		
		Input	Hidden	Output
NN0	1	8	0	1
NN1	2	5	3	1
NN2	3	4	2	1
NN3	4	4	2	1
NN4	5	3	2	1
NN5	6	2	1	1

Three series of learning cycles were made (1000, 2000 or 5000 learning cycles) to determine the weights of the 8 connections between the input and output parameters. The RMS (Root Mean Square) error is similar for all learning cycles and is equal to 0.25 (see table 4). This first step indicates 2

important parameters with one predominant: the stirring rate of emulsification step and the surfactant concentration.

Table 4: Details of weights of the input parameters for the output parameter vs learning cycles

Output parameter : Speed of clarification (%/min)			
Iterations	1000	2000	5000
Input parameters			
t_{em}	0.10	0.06	-0.05
S_{em}	-4.73	-4.76	-4.67
T_{em}°	0.50	0.31	0.02
T_{evap}°	0.30	0.07	-0.25
T_{sti}	0.03	0.04	0.04
C_s	-0.75	-0.84	-0.95
C_{co-s}	0.04	0.03	0.03
C_{af}	-0.15	-0.17	-0.21
RMS error	0.25	0.25	0.25

To improve RMS error and confirm these 2 important parameters for the speed of clarification, we built 5 new neural networks (see table 3: NN1 to NN5). In this case, we added in the architecture of our neural network a hidden layer composed of a variable number of hidden nodes, depending of number of input nodes. This second step, named cross-validation method, permit to split the training set into two: a set of 27 experimental data in the training set and a set of 1 experimental data in the validation set. The training set is used to calculate a predictive value corresponding to the validation set. The RMS error is calculated in table 5. The accuracy is given in table 6 and the figure 3 show the best result of networks (NN5) with 1.8%/min of accuracy for speed of clarification in a range of 6 to 43%/min. This validation confirms that stirring rate of emulsification step and surfactant concentration are the most important parameters which affect the speed of clarification.

Table 5: RMS error for each neural networks used for cross validation vs learning cycles

Neural Networks	RMS error	
	5000 iterations	10,000 iterations
NN1	0.08	0.06
NN2	0.06	0.05
NN3	0.07	0.06
NN4	0.05	0.05
NN5	0.05	0.05

Table 6: Results of the precision for all artificial neural networks in the validation process after 5000 or 10,000 learning cycles

Neural Networks	Accuracy (%/min)	
	5000 iterations	10,000 iterations
NN1	1.972	1.884
NN2	1.928	1.884
NN3	1.796	1.796
NN4	1.840	1.796
NN5	1.796	1.796

Figure 3: Validation agreement plot of ANN for speed of clarification. Line corresponds to perfect prediction and stars to values predicted by the neural networks.

3.3 Analyses of the aqueous dispersions

The QSPR method enables us to focus the study of the dispersion on only 2 parameters. So, we observe the influence of these two parameters on the particle size given by dynamic light scattering (DLS) and the stability of the dispersion given by LUMiFuge®. The morphology of the polymer particles is observed by transmission electron microscopy (TEM). First, we have to reduce foam formation during the emulsification step, so we have to determine the best concentration of co-surfactant (sorbitan monostearate). This co-surfactant act as anti-foam agent and we can observe a diminution of 5%v of foam with the addition of 0.12%w of this co-surfactant in the media. Figure 4 shows a minimum at this concentration for the mean diameter of particles (around 600 nm) and the dispersity (around 0.21). This dispersity is observed in the TEM image (see figure 5) with a mean diameter of particle between 70 and 800 nm.

Figure 4: Evolution of the mean diameter of particle and dispersity in function of co-surfactant concentration. The stirring rate of emulsification step is fixed to 7800 rpm.

Figure 5: TEM image of a dispersion comprising 0.52%w of PEI, 0.57%w of benzalkonium chloride and 0.12%w of co-surfactant. Stirring rate of emulsification step: 7800 rpm for 30 minutes.

If we fixed the surfactant concentration (benzalkonium chloride), we observe an important diminution of the particle size with the shear speed of emulsification step (see figure 6). This is consistent with the formulation process. The smallest the particle size, the most stable is the dispersion, so the best stirring rate of emulsification is 12 000 rpm with a dispersion stability of 7 hours given by DLS (see figure 7). After 7h, the particle size decreases by 5%.

Figure 6: Evolution of mean diameter of particle and dispersity as a function of stirring rate of the emulsification step. The surfactant and co-surfactant concentration are respectively set at 0.57%w and 0.12%w.

Figure 7: Evolution of mean diameter of particle and dispersity in function of time without stirring. The surfactant and co-surfactant concentration are respectively set at 0.57%w and 0.12%w and the stirring rate of the emulsification step is set at 12 000 rpm.

However, the destabilisation time, measured by the LUMiFuge[®] device, is a more efficient parameter to determine the stability of the dispersions. The SEPView v6 software calculated the speed of clarification of dispersions and simulated a destabilisation of 1 month in real time. At 7800 rpm of stirring rate of emulsification and 0.57% weight of surfactant, the 5% of destabilisation of dispersion is reached after at most 4h25 for 0.12% weight or 0.25% weight of co-surfactant. This is consistent with DLS analyses so the preferential co-surfactant concentration is 0.12% weight. Increasing surfactant concentration did not significantly increase the dispersion stability: 4h25 for 0.57% weight of surfactant and 4h37 for 1% weight of surfactant. So, the selected surfactant concentration was 0.57% weight. Therefore, the stability increases with the stirring rate of the emulsification step, which is consistent with a decrease of particle size in the media. The figure 8 shows the destabilisation time as a function of the stirring rate of the emulsification step. With a speed of 12 000 rpm, the dispersion reaches is stable for 6 hours before a sedimentation of 5% is observed. This is less than the DLS value but the LUMiFuge[®] accuracy is 2% and the one of DLS is around 16%.

Figure 8: Evolution of destabilisation time as a function of the stirring rate of emulsification. The surfactant and co-surfactant concentration are respectively set at 0.57%w and 0.12%w.

3.4 Characterization of thermoplastic sizing with this dispersion

In a first step, the sizing is tested on AFM carbon slab (1cm*1cm). The dispersion is put on carbon slab with a pipette, spread and the carbon slab is let in an oven at 100°C during 5 minutes to evaporate the water. Then, this carbon slab is observed by AFM and SEM. The height profile shows a roughness around 10 nm on the cross section defined in the AFM image (see figure 9). This can be representative of a relatively homogeneous film on this area. But on area of 20 μm^2 , we can observe a maximum height of 30 nm (see figure 9) and the SEM image confirms a non-homogeneous sizing. PEI particles partially merge but do not form a continuous film.

Figure 9: AFM image (left) and height profile (right) of PEI sizing on carbon slab. The dispersion is put on carbon slab and heated in oven at 100°C.

Figure 10: TEM image of PEI sizing on carbon slab. The dispersion is spread on a carbon slab and heated in oven at 100°C.

This dispersion is also tested on carbon fiber on a sizing line in factory. The schematic sizing line is described in figure 11. The speed of unwinding is 5 m/min and the oven temperature is fixed to 150°C.

Figure 11: Schematic sizing line in factory.

The AFM image (figure 12) shows a non-homogeneous sizing on carbon fiber and polymer patches between 10 to 50 nm height. This is coherent with the observations on carbon slab. Similarly, SEM image shows particles dispersed at the surface of carbon fiber (see figure 13). This indicates that the

sizing process maybe needs some adjustments to obtain a homogeneous film on the carbon fiber.

Figure 12: AFM image (left) and height profile (right) of PEI sizing on carbon fiber. The carbon fiber is dipped in a bath of PEI dispersion and heated in oven at 150°C.

Figure 13: SEM image of PEI sizing on carbon fiber. The carbon fiber is dipped in a bath of PEI dispersion and heated in oven at 150°C.

4 CONCLUSIONS

Stable eco-friendly dispersion was made and optimized by QSPR method. Two important parameters have been highlighted to affect the stability of the dispersion: the stirring rate of emulsification and the surfactant concentration. These parameters have been successfully adapted to optimize the stability of the dispersion. We succeeded in obtaining an aqueous dispersion stable around 6 hours with 0.5% w of thermoplastic polymer. This dispersion has been tested for sizing on carbon slab and carbon fiber. The AFM and SEM images show a non homogeneous sizing resulting from a non-optimized sizing process. Some works on sizing process and other type of aqueous sizing dispersion are in progress.

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